

WILDLIFE AND INTRUSION REPELLENT USING IOT

¹Manjunatha T N , ²Sathwik K S, ³Sharath K, ⁴Shreyas K V, ⁵Sudarshan T S

¹Professor, ^{2,3,4,5}Students

Department of CSE
East West Institute of Technology
Bengaluru, India

Abstract— One significant issue that puts human lives in jeopardy is the influx of wild animals. and costs enormous sums of money. People lose their crops, belongings, and possibly even their lives as a result. In this paper, a system that monitors using the Internet of Thing in the field to help detect wild animal intrusions on agricultural farms to be able to address this issue. Through an IoT application, the farmer receives an alert message. The ESP32 Module serves as the project's brain, while the ESP32 Camera, PIR sensors, and laser beams in addition to speakers and ultrasonic sounds, are employed in species-specific deterrence. The solar-powered system gathers important information about animal behaviour and intrusions, providing ideas for future growth and encouraging peaceful coexistence. The efficacy of The recommended approach has been looked at in relation to the photos of the intruder that were taken and the alarm that was sent out. Anyone can efficiently identify any kind of incursion around the field by using this provided methodology.

Keywords:- — Monitoring, Ultrasonic Sound, ESP32, PIR Sensor, Laser, Speaker, Solar panel, Intrusion, IoT.

1. INTRODUCTION

Animal crop raiding has become a prevalent human-animal conflict due to human encroachment on natural habitats and deforestation. Wild animals have the potential to assault farmers in the field and seriously harm agricultural crops.

There are often difficulties maintaining the delicate balance between human populations and animals. Conventional approaches to animal deterrent may be detrimental or ineffectual, and inadequate solutions expose humans and property to risk. We offer a ground-breaking solution to this problem: an Internet of Things (IoT)-powered Intelligent Wildlife and Intrusion Repellent System. This

creative system uses state-of-the-art technology to securely and effectively discourage the existence of unwanted animals, fostering peaceful coexistence between people and wildlife.

To enhance the security and protection of agricultural assets in rural areas, the project makes use of cutting-edge technology including the ESP32 CAMERA module, low-intensity lasers, ultrasonic modules, and machine learning algorithms.

The concept uses ultrasonic sound modules to create sound that deters rodents and other crop-damaging insects, and low-intensity lasers to scare away wild animals. The possible installation of a solar power supply system incorporates an environmentally conscientious strategy, encouraging sustainability and lowering dependency on traditional energy sources.

Imagine a system uses sensitive PIR sensors to automatically detect animal trespass and uses an onboard ESP32 camera module for identify the species. This real-time data is used by system to launch a species-specific, targeted reaction. The animal is startled and confused by a harmless green laser beam that is directed by a precision servo motor. Tailored to individual species, ultrasonic sounds offer an extra degree of deterrence without harming people or beneficial wildlife. To further deter infiltration, strong speakers can also broadcast alerts or even animal distress calls.

However, t His framework provides greater than simply quick fixes. It also collects important information about species types, deployed deterrents, and intrusions. It is powered by a sustainable solar power source.

Through the use of a centralized platform, this real-time data is available, offering vital insights into animal behavior and facilitating ongoing system effectiveness optimization. The careful balancing act between people and wildlife has advanced significantly thanks to our novel Wildlife and Intrusion Repellent System. Puts stainability and safety first, providing a compassionate and practical response to the problems caused by animal incursion. We can build a future

where people and wildlife coexist together, safeguarding one without sacrificing the other, by embracing the potential of the Internet of Things.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Reference [1] Using a line-following vehicle, this study proposes an IoT mechanism for detecting intrusions that seeks to accomplish automatic monitoring of encroachments. Our project's solar-battery systems for continuous operations have the ability to reduce their reliance on grid power [cite solar power scaling report]. But false alarms continue to be a problem that needs to be addressed with thorough sensor calibration, image verification checks, and testing various deterrents on real animals.

Reference [2] Although it is noted that deterrence measures should be integrated into the architecture of Section IV-C of our methodology, this study concentrates on alert systems for the detection of intrusions rather than doing so. However, the ESP32-CAM they are using is compatible with our hardware designs, making it simple to integrate software for local categorization prior to cloud alerts. Although there is a chance of false alarms, the multi-stage alert setup presented here can help lower the number of unnecessary system activations by allowing you to adjust different thresholds for each level of alerts.

Reference [3] This paper's common goal is to use Internet of Things automation to lessen the harmful effects of animal incursions. As we cover in Section III-B of our strategy, solar energy harvesting may be able to reduce the Requirement that AC mains electricity.

The practical application of repellents that are effective but safe for various species can also be improved by further research, as suggested by our tiered mechanisms that activate based on AI classification confidence levels.

Reference [4] This research on IoT-based wildlife infringement identification draws attention to problems such as limited nighttime surveillance and distance computations that depend on stationary camera locations. By utilizing cutting-edge sensors like thermal cameras in conjunction with PIR sensors, the suggested system seeks to overcome these constraints by enabling motion detections around-the-clock and transmitting alerts to numerous mobile devices. Wider off-grid additionally, regions are covered with repositionable trail cameras, which are powered by periodically changing battery banks.

Reference [5] This paper's methodology, deep convolutional neural networks are used in this and transfer learning to automate animal classification, substantially supports the computer vision strategy intended for precise species detection. When frequently fine-tuning the model on fresh local wildlife data, their recommendation that a system must be calibrated on a regular basis for optimal performance will be crucial.

Essentially, the reviewed literature supports the path of

technology while drawing attention to common issues that require thought, such as the need for extra sensors to increase robustness, periodic maintenance requirements, and ethical ways to provide 24x7 monitoring.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

By utilizing cutting-edge technologies, the current system is intended to alleviate the growing conflict between human populations and animals in India. It creates an automatic intrusion detection and repelling system by combining the Things Network (IoT) with Artificial Intelligence (AI). The Raspberry Pi, a low-cost, portable computer, and passive infrared motion (PIR) sensors for motion detection are among the hardware parts of system. The technology employs a cutting-edge object detection method called YOLOv3 model to identify wild animals in real-time and activates a camera to record live video streaming upon detecting an intruder. When a wild animal is detected, the system minimizes the potentially dangerous effects of human-wildlife confrontations by setting off a buzzer and headlights to drive the animal back into the forest. This creative strategy not only offers a more effective and economic solution compared to traditional methods but also demonstrates the potential of AI and IoT in mitigating the adverse impacts of human-wildlife interactions.

4. OBJECTIVE OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Using IoT capabilities for real-time detection and alerting of animal intrusions within human settlement boundaries, along with gentle repellent techniques to discourage proximity while ~~compassionate solution that strikes a balance, between the main objective of driving environmental sustainability, wildlife security, and agriculture/livestock protection. The variety of technologies is~~ sensor fusion approach, precision intrusion detection is achieved by utilising PIR and camera traps to consistently detect animal breaches in perimeter zones. (2) Immediate notifications via cellular connectivity to alert interested parties in farms, villages, and conservation areas, allowing for swiftly planned actions (3) Employing embedded machine learning algorithms to classify and activate an assortment of non-invasive auditory, visual, and sensory deterrents according to the most common wild species in the area; (4) Using smarter edge computing and responsiveness to develop an ethically sound and compassionate solution that strikes a balance between the needs of environmental sustainability, wildlife security, and agriculture/livestock protection. The variety of technologies is designed to provide scalable setups that satisfy particular needs for rural use cases.

5. METHODOLOGY

The suggested system uses an ensemble Internet of Things strategy that combines edge intelligence, deterrent mechanisms, and sensors to continuously monitor and mitigate

wildlife incursions in border areas. To record movement within the perimeter zones, PIR sensors and weatherproof trail cameras are positioned in critical locations. Sensor data is sent via a LoRa WAN network to a gateway node, which then uses cellular 4G to send the events to a cloud IoT platform. Video from the cameras is also streamed to a Raspberry Pi device at the edge over a local Wi-Fi mesh network. To ensure that differentiate between different wild animals and human intruders, the Pi uses a TensorFlow Lite machine learning model to interpret the real-time video streams. Using Teachable Machine, the model is trained on a dataset of pertinent wildlife photos and then transformed for optimal inference.

Considering the outcomes of the classification, appropriate deterrent measures are initiated. Problematic wildlife is targeted by strobe lights, distress calls, and ultrasonic tones; if people are spotted, the owner receives an SMS notice. Grafana dashboards are used to log the sensor measurements and response actions to a cloud timeseries database for long-term analytics. To optimize efficiency, patterns are used to refine automation rules and retrain cadence. Because of their modular architecture, parts including speakers, cameras, and networking modules can be changed to meet different coverage requirements and field conditions. Ongoing operation is made possible in part by solar panels. The system facilitates sustainable cohabitation by reducing detection-response latency through edge intelligence, offering persistence through renewable power, and striking a balance between security and pragmatic ethics.

6. CONCLUSION

The "Wildlife and Intrusion Repellent Using IoT" project aims to protect cattle, wildlife, and human settlements by developing an automated system that is capable of identifying and repel wild animals without causing harm. The system, which utilizes IoT technology, offers advantages including

robust data analysis, scalability, application in various fields, reduction of human-animal conflicts, and real-time monitoring. These qualities make Internet of Things (IoT)-based solutions a very promising and successful strategy for improving wildlife management.

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